

Acceptable Use Policy for the EOSC Open Science Observatory

V2.0 on 16 June 2025

This Acceptable Use Policy (AUP) defines the rules and conditions that govern your access to and use (including transmission, processing, and storage of data) of the Services as granted by the EOSC Track project [<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101148217>]. for the purpose of collecting, analysing, and sharing data to monitor the EOSC readiness of Member States and Associated Countries, the implementation of and contributions to the EOSC Partnership, and national and institutional policies that are relevant for EOSC via the EOSC Open Science Observatory [<https://www.eoscobservatory.eu/>]:

- You shall only use the Services in a manner consistent with the policies and for the purposes described above, show consideration towards other users, and collaborate in the resolution of issues arising from your use of the Services
 - You shall only use the Services for lawful purposes and not breach, attempt to breach, nor circumvent administrative or security controls
 - You shall respect intellectual property and confidentiality agreements
 - You shall protect your access credentials (such as passwords, private keys, or multi-factor tokens) and no intentional sharing is permitted
 - You shall keep your registered information correct and up to date
 - You shall promptly report known or suspected security breaches, compromise of credentials, or misuse to the security contact stated below and to the relevant issuing authorities
 - Reliance on the Services shall only be to the extent specified by any applicable service level agreements listed below and use without such agreements is at your own risk
 - Your personal data will be processed in accordance with the Data Protection Policies referenced below
 - Your use of the Services may be restricted or suspended (for administrative, operational, or security reasons) without prior notice and without compensation
- If you violate these rules, you may be liable for the consequences, which may include a report being made to your home organisation or to law enforcement.

The administrative contact for this AUP is: <admin@openaire.eu>

The security contact for this AUP is: <security-team@openaire.eu>

The Data Protection Policies located at:

[<https://zenodo.org/records/10825527>]